

NOTES

Chemical Investigations on *Bignonia diversifolia*

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The leaves of *Bignonia diversifolia* (Fam. Bignoneaceae) contain ursolic acid and stigmasterol.

Dried and powdered leaves of *B. diversifolia* were extracted with chloroform for 20 hr., solvent was removed and the green resinous residue was taken up in ether. The clear ether solution was washed with cold 3 per cent aqueous sodium hydroxide solution and then with water. The dried (Na_2SO_4) ether solution on evaporation gave a gummy residue.

The above gummy neutral residue was chromatographed over a column of alumina and elution with benzene-chloroform (1 : 1) furnished stigmasterol, m.p. and mixed m.p. 168°, $[\alpha]_D - 48^\circ$ (Lit.¹ m.p. 170°, $[\alpha]_D - 49^\circ$); acetate, m.p. 143°, $[\alpha]_D - 53^\circ$ (Lit.¹ m.p. 145°, $[\alpha]_D - 55^\circ$).

The alkali washed portion of the ether solution was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid. The precipitated solid acid was extracted with ether. The ethereal solution after washing and drying was concentrated to a small volume and the residue thus obtained was chromatographed over silica gel. The petrol and the benzene fractions afforded much oil whereas the chloroform eluates furnished a solid m.p. 275°, which on crystallisation from ethanol gave needles, m.p. 279°, $[\alpha]_D + 69^\circ$ (Found : C, 78.81; H, 10.52; Calc. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{48}\text{O}_3$: C, 78.95; H, 10.53%). This was found to be identical with an authentic sample of ursolic acid from mixed m.p. (Lit.², m.p. 286°, $[\alpha]_D + 70^\circ$) and mixed T.L.C.

The above acid on methylation with an ethereal solution of diazomethane and usual work up furnished methyl ester, m.p. 168° (Found : C, 79.18; H, 10.44; Calc. for $\text{C}_{31}\text{H}_{50}\text{O}_3$: C, 79.15; H, 10.64%). This was found to be identical with an authentic sample of methyl ursolate from mixed m.p. (Lit.² m.p. 171°) and mixed I.R.

The acid on acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine followed by chromatography over silica gel gave acetyl derivative of ursolic acid, m.p. 286° (Lit.² m.p. 292°).

Methyl ursolate on acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine in the usual manner gave acetyl methyl ursolate, m.p. 242° (Lit.² m.p. 246°); the same compound was also obtained on methylation of acetyl derivative of ursolic acid with an ethereal solution of diazomethane followed by chromatography over alumina.

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A cold solution of ursolic acid in dry pyridine was added to a slurry of chromic acid-pyridine complex³. The reaction product obtained on usual processing was dissolved in benzene and chromatographed over a column of alumina. The benzene eluate gave a solid which on crystallisation from chloroform-methanol mixture gave ursolic acid, m.p. 192° (Lit.⁴ m.p. 191–93°), which showed positive Zimmermann test⁵.

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